

The Advantages and Difficulties of Teaching Grade 11 Geography (Book Series Connecting Knowledge to Life)

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ABSTRACT: Innovation is an indispensable element in education. The 2023-2024 school year marks the beginning of the application of new 11th grade textbooks. Implementing new textbooks brings many initial difficulties for both teachers and students. This article focuses on understanding and analyzing the advantages and disadvantages of teaching 11th grade Geography according to the book series Connecting knowledge to life. Thereby, the article aims to help educational managers, teachers and students make the most of the benefits of new textbooks and find solutions to current challenges. This makes an important contribution to improving education quality and learning efficiency in the context of the 2018 education reform program.

KEYWORD: Geography, grade 11, connecting knowledge to life, general education 2018.

I. INTRODUCTION

The 2023 - 2024 school year marks an important event when the 11th Geography textbook in the Connecting Knowledge with Life series is officially introduced into teaching under the 2018 education reform program. This reform program aims to modernize the content and teaching methods, with the goal of improving the quality of education, helping students develop comprehensively in knowledge, skills and qualities. In this context, the application of the new Grade 11 Geography textbook brings many opportunities and challenges for teachers and students.

Researching the advantages and disadvantages of teaching Grade 11 Geography according to the book series Connecting knowledge to life not only helps evaluate the effectiveness of new textbooks but also provides valuable information to improve the process. Teaching. This is especially important in the modern educational context, when traditional teaching methods are gradually being replaced by advanced, student-centered methods. Understanding the advantages and disadvantages will help educational managers, teachers and students take full advantage of the benefits of new textbooks and find solutions to current challenges. This has also been emphasized by John Hattie (2008) that researching and understanding the advantages and disadvantages of teaching is the key to improving the quality of education and helping educators, administrators and students make the most of their teaching. Make the most of modern learning tools. Sharing the same opinion, David Lambert and John Morgan (2015) said: "In the field of Geography education, the importance of evaluating textbooks and teaching methods to improve teaching effectiveness is. They emphasized that research and understanding of the challenges and opportunities in Geography teaching are necessary to apply innovative and student-centered methods".

II. RESEARCH METHODS

To conduct this research, the author used the document research method to research issues related to the 2018 general education curriculum, general teaching methods and Geography teaching methods. in particular, at the same time using additional survey methods (Survey of 138 teachers directly teaching Geography 11 in many different localities in the Northern region, such as Thai Nguyen, Hoa Binh, Yen Bai, Nam Dinh, Cao Bang, Bac Ninh... during the school year 2023 - 2024) to grasp more practical difficulties and advantages in teaching Geography 11 (book series Connecting knowledge to life).

III. RESEARCH CONTENT AND DISCUSSION

1. Curriculum and subject content

1.1. General education program 2018

The 2018 general education program was born in the context that the country has achieved important economic achievements but still faces many challenges in the quality of human resources and economic competition. At the same time, the fourth industrial

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revolution and global changes in the environment and society pose an urgent need for educational innovation to meet the needs of sustainable development and international integration (Huong, 2019).

The goal of the birth of the 2018 general education program is to create a fundamental and comprehensive change in the quality and effectiveness of education, combining literacy teaching, people training and career orientation. The program aims to comprehensively develop the qualities and abilities of students, helping them become responsible citizens, creative workers and capable of lifelong learning, meeting the country's sustainable development requirements. in the context of globalization and the new industrial revolution (Ministry of Education and Training, 2018).

1.2. Grade 11 Geography program

Geography is content that helps students gain basic knowledge about nature, people, economics and society of countries around the world, and especially about Vietnam, with the aim of forming, develop scientific qualities and abilities, especially love of homeland and country; Proper behavior towards the natural and social environment; career orientation ability; to form a citizen's personality, ready to contribute to the cause of building and protecting the Fatherland.

The content and teaching plan are structured as follows:

Table 1. Content flow and teaching plan

Content	Teaching plan(period)	
	Theory	Practice
Part I. SOME WORLD SOCIO-ECONOMIC ISSUES	6	2
Differences in socio-economic development between groups of countries	2	0
Globalization, economic regionalization and global security	4	1
Knowledge economy	0	1
PART II. REGIONAL AND NATIONAL GEOGRAPHY	forty six	9
Latin America region	5	1
European Union (EU)	4	1
Southeast Asia region	7	1
Southwest Asia region	4	1
United States of America	6	0
Russia	5	1
Japan	5	1
People's Republic of China (China)	5	1
Australia (Australia)	0	2
Republic of South Africa	5	0
Review and test	7	0
TOTAL	70	

Source: Ministry of Education and Training, 2018.

The content circuit in the Geography 11 program includes 2 parts: Part I is general socio-economic issues (accounting for 8 periods, equivalent to 11.4% of the time), Part II is geography of regions and countries. (55 hours, equivalent to 78.6% of the time). The contents in Part II, although covering different regions and countries, are all designed according to a stable structure: from geographical location and natural conditions to population, society and economy. Establishing a stable and repetitive structure helps students easily access and understand each piece of content, creating a coherent knowledge system. When lessons are designed in a repeating pattern, students can easily remember and review knowledge, linking new information with previously learned knowledge. This not only develops memory ability but also helps students practice comparison and analysis skills, through comparing the geographical, social and economic characteristics of different regions in a systematic way. system. In addition, a stable structure also helps students feel more confident when approaching new content, thereby increasing their motivation to learn. At the same time, it is also easier for teachers to prepare lessons, test and evaluate and answer students' questions, thanks to a clear and coherent teaching system (Robert Marzano, 2012).

In addition to the core content shown in the 11th Geography textbook, the Geography 2018 GDT program also has learning topics shown in the 11th Geography Study Topics textbook for students who are inclined to choose to study. a number of learning topics suitable to your own aspirations and the school's organizational conditions. Topics are built to expand and improve knowledge to meet the requirements of deep differentiation at the high school level; At the same time, it helps students understand more deeply the role of geography in real life and careers related to geography so that students have a basis for career orientation and continue to self-study geography throughout their lives. Geography 11 learning topics include:

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Table 2. Geography learning topics grade 11

Content	Number of periods
Topic 11.1. Some issues about Southeast Asia	15
– Mekong River Commission (MRC)	10
– Peaceful cooperation in exploiting the East Sea	5
Topic 11.2. Some problems about world tourism	10
– World tourism resources	3
– Some popular types of tourism and tourism development trends in the world today	5
- Career orientation	2
Topic 11.3. The fourth industrial revolution (4.0)	10
- Main content	4
– Impact on world socio-economic development	6

Source: Le Huynh, 2023

1.3. Geography textbook grade 11 (book series Connecting knowledge to life)

1.3.1. Book characteristics

Geography 11 textbook is a learning material for 11th grade students following the general education program. In addition to the cover pages and sub-cover pages, this book has 167 pages, compiled according to the requirements of the Ministry of Education and Training, to provide knowledge about socio-economic geography on a world scale and each country, continents. The book's outstanding feature is the system of image channels and text channels that are scientifically and intuitively designed.

+ The text channel includes main text segments, presented clearly, logically and easily to understand, helping students grasp the lesson content effectively. Important concepts and definitions are bolded or italicized for emphasis and easy reference.

+ The image channel is very diverse and rich, including maps, charts, illustrations, data tables and scientific drawings. These images not only help illustrate the lesson content but also play an important role in helping students visualize geographical issues more clearly. For example, maps of the world and major economic regions, statistical charts on population, economy, climate, etc., are all designed in detail and with vivid colors.

In addition to the main information channel, there are text channels and image channels, and there is also an information channel. This channel does not stop at text and images but also includes suggestive questions, practice exercises, and tests to assess student capacity. These sections help students consolidate what they have learned, while also developing analysis, evaluation and problem-solving skills. At the end of the book, a glossary and transcription table is designed to help students clearly understand and remember specialized concepts, reduce difficulties when accessing new terms, and support accurate pronunciation. with foreign words, helping students learn more effectively (Norman Graves, 2000).

Figure 1: Geography textbook grade 11 (Connecting knowledge to life)

1.3.2. Lesson structure

Geography 11 textbook (a series of books connecting knowledge with life) is designed with 31 lessons: 21 theory lessons, 10 practice lessons. Each lesson is carried out in 1 - 3 class periods, each lesson solves a problem of the section. Each lesson is organized into four specific activities (each activity has its own logo):

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- Introductory activities take place before learning new knowledge, including problem situations, identifying learning tasks, or problems that need to be solved related to the lesson.
 - Activities to create new knowledge include content items and activities that help students acquire knowledge. The lesson is divided into two routes: main and secondary. The main route contains key content, including text channels (information, documents) and visual channels (maps, charts, pictures, data tables) along with questions and exercises. Secondary routes, such as the section "Do you know?", provide expanded or advanced knowledge, helping to clarify the main route content.
 - Practice activities include questions, exercises, and practice to consolidate knowledge and practice skills associated with newly learned knowledge.
 - Application activities are learning situations and tasks to creatively apply and solve practical situations associated with lesson content.
- After each theoretical lesson, there will usually be a practice lesson to consolidate knowledge and develop skills for students. As follows:

Figure 2: Lesson content structure (Connecting knowledge to life)

Table 3. Statistics of practice exercises in Geography textbook grade 11 (Knowledge-to-life connection set)

No	Practice
1	Learn about the opportunities and challenges of globalization and economic regionalization
2	Write a report on the characteristics and manifestations of the knowledge economy
3	Write a report on the socio-economic development situation in the Federal Republic of Brazil
4	Write a report on the industrial development of the Federal Republic of Germany
5	Learn about foreign economic activities of Southeast Asia
6	Write a report on the oil problem of Southwest Asia
7	Learn about the oil and gas exploitation industry of the Russian Federation
8	Write a report on Japan's foreign economic activities
9	Write a report on the changes in China's coastal economy
10	Learn about Australia's economy

Source: Geography textbook grade 11 (Knowledge connection to life)

Regarding practical exercises, the variety of practical exercises is not high, focusing more on developing report writing skills (6/10 exercises). This is both an advantage and a difficulty for teaching:

- + Advantages: Students and teachers can practice the same skill over and over again.
- + Difficulties: Difficulties for teachers in organizing teaching, requiring diversity, changing methods and ways of organizing teaching to avoid boredom in lessons.

Thus, the Geography 11 program and content are designed scientifically, systematically and intuitively, creating favorable conditions for teaching and learning Geography, helping students master knowledge and develop skills. The outstanding advantages can be seen as:

- + Streamlined knowledge
- + The video channel is intuitive, vivid, and suitable for students
- + Many activities to develop capacity

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- + Questions for practice and application
- + Easy to learn, easy to teach
- + Rich digital ecosystem

2. Equipment and facilities

Equipment and facilities play an important role in improving the quality of teaching and learning Geography. They not only create favorable conditions for teachers to convey knowledge effectively, but also help students absorb lessons more quickly and intuitively. The use of modern equipment such as projectors, electronic maps, and practical geography tools helps make lectures lively and easy to understand. At the same time, fully equipped functional classrooms and comfortable learning environments create active learning spaces that encourage student interaction and practice.

According to the survey, currently in high schools, special attention is paid to equipment for teaching in general and for private geography: 100% of schools are equipped with projectors/televisions, other electronic devices to support teaching and learning in a lively and intuitive way, students can easily follow images, videos, and digital documents related to the lesson. Equipping classrooms with more and more complete teaching equipment will help enhance practical learning experiences and facilitate hands-on activities.

In addition, high schools also pay great attention to digital documents and learning materials. According to recent reports and research, about 60-70% of high schools in Vietnam have applied digital documents and learning materials in teaching and learning. Digital learning materials include digital learning materials such as ebooks, video lectures, and learning applications that help students easily access and review knowledge anytime, anywhere. Thanks to that, students are not only limited to classroom hours but can also self-study and improve their knowledge at their own pace. In addition, diverse resources provided from many different channels help students expand their understanding and have a multi-dimensional view of geographical issues, thereby developing critical thinking and in-depth analysis ability. Integrating documents and digital learning materials into the curriculum not only enriches learning content but also stimulates students' excitement and creativity in the learning process.

In addition, to increase the quality of teaching and create the highest efficiency in teaching, high schools have been gradually upgrading school facilities to be the most spacious and modern, creating favorable conditions for students. Students have the most comfortable learning environment: tables, chairs, lighting, space, lamps, fans, ... are equipped in the best possible conditions. Completeness and modernity not only help teachers convey knowledge effectively but also create favorable conditions for students to absorb and apply knowledge into practice.

3. School, family and society

Teaching is not only an interaction between teachers and students, but is also strongly influenced by schools, parents and society. These elements together create a rich, multi-dimensional educational environment, helping to optimize the learning process and comprehensive development of students.

3.1.1. School

School administrators play an important role in designing and implementing curriculum, building and implementing clear policies and directions to support subject teaching. This includes providing adequate teaching materials and equipment such as maps, projectors, and computers, helping teachers have the best conditions to teach effectively. Modern equipment not only helps teachers convey knowledge more effectively, but also helps students more easily access and understand geographical concepts.

In addition, the Board of Directors also plays an important role in organizing training sessions and seminars to improve professional capacity for Geography teachers, helping them update new knowledge and teaching methods. This not only helps teachers keep up with changes in the curriculum but also encourages creativity and innovation in teaching methods. Training sessions and seminars also create opportunities for teachers to exchange and learn from colleagues and experts, thereby improving the quality of teaching. Administrators also play an important role in creating a positive learning environment, supporting extracurricular activities, field trips, and establishing Geography clubs to encourage student participation and interest in the subject. These activities not only help students consolidate theoretical knowledge but also practice practical skills and enhance thinking and creativity. Thanks to the support and proper direction from the Board of Directors, the Geography teaching process becomes more lively, practical and effective, contributing to improving the quality of comprehensive education in the school.

However, according to surveys at high schools, the Board of Directors often pays little attention to the subject Geography. The organization of seminars, seminars, professional and extracurricular activities is mostly due to the initiative of the subject group. The school board only creates conditions for Geography teachers to conduct professional training when requested or summoned by the Department. This is also a difficulty for the Geography subject, because lack of support and direction from the Board of Directors can make it difficult for teachers to improve the quality of teaching and motivate students.

3.1.2. Family

Families play an important role in supporting students in learning Geography. Parents can make an important contribution by providing reminders and facilitating learning at home. A quiet study space, fully equipped with necessary books and learning tools will help students focus more on their studies. Creating a reasonable timetable specifically for studying Geography is also very

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important, helping students form regular and organized study habits. Furthermore, close coordination between parents and schools is an important factor in improving students' learning quality. Through parent meetings, meetings and direct discussions with teachers, parents can grasp their children's learning situation and support them in overcoming difficulties, and at the same time work with the school to find solutions. come up with effective measures to improve learning outcomes in Geography. Parents can also contribute to Geography teaching by providing additional learning materials, reference resources and organizing related extracurricular activities. Instructing students to read reference books, watch documentary programs about geography, or participate in field trips organized by their families, will help students expand their knowledge and understanding of the subject. These practical experiences not only enrich knowledge but also help students have a deeper and more comprehensive view of the world around them. In addition, encouragement from family is an important source of motivation to help students develop passion and interest in Geography. When parents show interest in their children's learning and appreciate their students' efforts and achievements, they will feel more confident and motivated in learning. This support not only creates a positive learning environment but also contributes to forming a positive, persistent and progressive learning attitude in each student.

However, currently parents' interest in their children's Geography learning is not high, the main interest and attention is focused on subjects such as Math, Literature, Foreign Languages, and other important exam subjects. . This may be due to insufficient awareness of the importance of Geography in developing comprehensive knowledge and skills for students. This lack of understanding can lead to an underestimation of the role Geography plays in students' daily lives and personal development. Therefore, teaching and learning Geography has not really been promoted. Lack of interest and investment from parents is a major limitation in the process of teaching and learning Geography. This can lead to a lack of student motivation and interest in the subject, reducing the effectiveness of the teaching and learning process. To improve this situation, there needs to be increased information and importance of Geography for parents. Activities such as seminars, meetings between schools and parents, or community education programs can help parents better recognize and understand the importance of Geography for overall development. student representation. At the same time, it is necessary to create policies and measures to stimulate the interest and active participation of parents in their children's Geography teaching and learning process.

3.1.3. Society

Society plays an important role in strongly influencing the process of teaching and learning Geography. Society's awareness and perspective on this subject directly affects the way educational programs are designed and implemented, as well as the level of society's investment in the subject. For example, when society is not fully aware of important issues such as climate change and environmental pollution, teaching these topics in Geography is also not appreciated. This results in teachers and students not receiving the attention and investment needed to research and understand pressing environmental issues. Or cultural values and attitudes, along with local perspectives, also strongly influence the way Geography is taught and perceived.

In Vietnamese society, teaching Geography is facing a rather big challenge, which is the underestimation of the importance of this subject. Although Geography plays an important role in helping students understand the world around them and develop comprehensive thinking, many people still do not fully realize the value of the subject, and society does not truly understand it. Appreciate the role of Geography as a subject. This directly affects the quality of teaching and learning Geography, reducing opportunities for students to access important knowledge and skills that this subject brings. Therefore, to improve the situation, there need to be measures to raise society's awareness of the importance of Geography. Media campaigns, education and teacher training programs, along with adjusting education policies, can all contribute to changing social attitudes, thereby improving the quality of subject teaching and learning. Geography helps students develop comprehensively and have solid knowledge about the world around them.

4. Teachers and students

4.1. Teacher

Teachers play an important role in ensuring the quality of teaching Geography. Teachers' professional qualifications are considered a key factor determining the quality of teaching. A deep understanding of subject content along with the ability to convey knowledge clearly and vividly are important factors in creating a positive and effective learning environment. At the same time, teaching experience also plays an important role, helping teachers grasp the needs and characteristics of each student, thereby applying the most appropriate teaching methods to optimize the learning process. .

Normally in high schools, new teachers are assigned to teach the first grade classes, and long-time, experienced teachers will arrange to teach the last grade classes because it related to graduation exams and other important exams.

In the 2023 - 2024 school year, according to a survey of 138 teachers directly teaching Geography 11 in many different localities in the Northern provinces, it shows:

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Table 4. Seniority of teachers directly teaching Geography grade 11

Seniority of work	12 years		3 – 10 years		Over 10 years	
	Quantity	%	Quantity	%	Quantity	%
Number of teachers	28	20.3	68	49.3	42	30.4

Source: Author's survey

Thus, the majority of teachers teaching Geography grade 11 are teachers with teaching experience, (from 3 to 10 years prevail). That is also an advantage for teaching Geography. These are also teachers who have taught through the 2006 curriculum textbooks, so they will have experience and be able to compare the 2006 reform curriculum with 2018.

Besides professional qualifications, the ability to update new teaching methods and enthusiasm for work also play important roles. Usually this is easy to find in young teachers, because their health, dynamism, and ability to grasp information technology are also quicker, so they are able to grasp and change teaching methods. New easier and more convenient. As the survey results above show, teachers directly teaching Geography grade 11 are usually relatively young teachers with about 3 to 10 years of experience. They are still very energetic and have the ability to grasp technology quickly. This is also an advantage in teaching Geography grade 11 when accessing modern teaching methods, or technological teaching applications.

4.2. Pupil

Students are objects of perception. Grade 11 students have developed better logical and abstract thinking abilities, helping them grasp complex geographical concepts and analyze phenomena deeply. This ability allows teachers to design Geography lessons with in-depth content so that students can participate in data analysis activities, evaluate impacts and come up with solutions based on their knowledge. learned, thereby creating exciting and effective learning sessions. At the same time, 11th grade students often have a higher self-awareness of learning and are interested in social and environmental issues. This creates favorable conditions for teachers to integrate practical and urgent topics into lessons. For example, issues of globalization, global security, etc. Students' interest and responsibility for these issues will increase educational effectiveness and help them apply knowledge into practice. In addition, the current generation of students is proficient in using information technology, which brings many benefits in teaching and learning Geography. Teachers can integrate digital tools such as digital maps, GIS software, and online resources into their lessons. Students can conduct research projects, collect and analyze geographic data through these tools, thereby improving their understanding and practical skills. The use of technology also helps make lessons more lively and attractive, attracting students' attention and excitement. However, the important thing is that personalizing learning to suit each student's needs and interests is quite a challenge. Each student has their own interests, strengths and weaknesses, and finding a teaching method that suits each child requires teachers to have a deep understanding of the student and the ability to make flexible adjustments. In a large classroom, this becomes especially difficult, requiring teachers to have good classroom management skills and to effectively use continuous assessment methods to monitor student progress. In addition, information technology brings many benefits, not all schools have enough resources and equipment to deploy effectively. Lack of computers, unstable internet, or lack of specialized software can be major obstacles in applying modern teaching methods. Teachers need to be creative and flexible in using available resources, and sometimes have to rely on traditional methods to ensure all students can participate and learn.

Based on the advantages and disadvantages in teaching Geography grade 11 as analyzed above, there needs to be an orientation for teaching this subject more effectively.

5. Orientation for teaching Geography grade 11 (book series Connecting knowledge to life)

5.1. Orientation on teaching methods:

- Create an active and creative learning environment: Teachers play the role of organizer, guide and encourage students, creating a friendly learning environment. Students are encouraged to learn proactively, positively and creatively, focusing on cultivating self-study ability. In this way, students not only acquire knowledge but also develop self-study skills and independent thinking ability.
- Linking lessons with reality through experiential activities: Linking geography lessons with local, country and world realities through experiential activities helps students apply knowledge in practice. solving local environmental, economic and social problems. This not only helps students develop awareness but also practice skills and form necessary qualities and abilities.
- Diversify teaching methods: Teachers flexibly combine advanced teaching methods with specific methods of geography such as using maps, diagrams, statistics, charts, and pictures. photos, models, observations and fieldwork. At the same time, improve traditional methods such as presentations and questions and answers to promote student positivity.
- Diverse and flexible teaching organization: Teaching forms are diverse and flexible, combining individual, group and class teaching. Students have the opportunity to study in class, outdoors and in practice, participate in field activities, tours, local surveys, collect, systematize information, display, introduce and exhibit. These forms help students experience reality and develop practical skills.
- Effectively exploit geography teaching aids: Teachers organize, guide and create conditions for students to explore, discover and gain knowledge from teaching aids such as maps, atlases, and pictures. photos, models, monitoring and measuring instruments, documents and materials. Students are encouraged to exploit information from the internet to serve their studies and practice skills

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in processing and presenting geographical information using information and communication technology. Making your own teaching equipment and applying information technology in teaching such as creating a learning website, building a system of lessons, exercises, practice and testing with appropriate software, creating videos Clips introducing geographical objects and phenomena are also promoted.

5.2. Orientation on assessing learning outcomes

- Providing accurate and timely information: Evaluating educational results in Geography aims to provide accurate and timely information about the level of meeting program requirements and student progress. This information helps guide learning activities, supporting students to achieve better results.
- Based on quality and capacity requirements: The criteria for evaluating students' educational results are built based on the quality and capacity requirements specified in the overall program and program. geography. This ensures that the assessment accurately reflects the educational objectives set.
- Comprehensive assessment of skills: In addition to assessing knowledge, it is necessary to focus on assessing students' skills such as: working with maps, atlases, charts, diagrams, data tables, pictures, Observe, collect, process and systematize information. Students also need to be assessed on their ability to use outdoor learning tools, technology and information communications in learning. This assessment helps ensure students can apply knowledge to specific situations.
- Diversify assessment forms: To ensure comprehensive assessment, it is necessary to diversify assessment forms and increase regular assessment for all students. Assessment forms include tests, project assignments, field observations, presentations, and group exercises. Combining teacher assessment with student self-assessment and mutual assessment is also an effective method to develop students' self-awareness and collaboration abilities.
- Use both qualitative and quantitative methods: Educational outcomes need to be assessed using both qualitative and quantitative methods through regular and periodic assessments. This helps synthesize overall assessment results of students' qualities, abilities and progress. This comprehensive assessment method provides a clear view of student development, leading to timely and effective improvement measures.

5.3. Orientation on teaching equipment

In teaching geography with the orientation of developing qualities and abilities, teaching equipment plays a very important role. Teaching equipment for Geography includes:

- Maps, geographical atlases, geographical atlases.
- Charts, diagrams, diagrams, slices.
- Documents and materials (statistical yearbooks, socio-economic data,...).
- Pictures of objects, natural geographical phenomena and socio-economic geography.
- Models and specimens.
- Tools and equipment (area, thermometer, hygrometer, barometer, camera,...).
- Teaching software, video clips; Digital libraries contain archives of geography teaching materials

IV. CONCLUDE

Teaching with the Geography 11 book series (Connecting knowledge to life) brings many significant advantages but also faces many difficulties that need to be overcome. On the one hand, this series of books provides modern teaching materials and methods, helping students grasp geographical knowledge in an intuitive and vivid way, while also developing critical thinking skills and the ability to apply knowledge. apply knowledge into practice. Integrating experiential activities, using information technology and linking lessons with real life helps students become more interested in the subject, thereby improving educational effectiveness. However, challenges still exist. The diversity of student levels, the pressure from heavy curriculum and exams, along with limited resources and equipment are significant obstacles. To overcome these difficulties, there needs to be flexibility and creativity in teaching methods, support from educational agencies and efforts from both teachers and students.

In general, the Geography 11 book series (Connecting knowledge to life) has been making an important contribution to innovating teaching methods, towards the goal of comprehensive and sustainable education. To achieve the highest effectiveness, teaching needs to be continuously adjusted and improved, meeting the needs and abilities of students, while maximizing the potential of modern books and teaching methods. .

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